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Impact of Immunization Against Communicable Diseases among Under-Five-Year Children in Zaakpon Community, Khana Local Government Area of Rivers State

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Abstract

This research focused on the impact of immunization against communicable diseases among under-five-year children in Zaakpon Community, Khana Local Government Area of Rivers State. The descriptive study design was used in a retrospective research setting. The researchers made use of parents of under-five children as the population of response in the study to substitute for the target population (the under-5 children). The population of 1,300 parents of under-five children was purposively chosen. A sample size of 306 parents of under-five children was drawn out of it. The major instrument for data collection was a well-structured and validated questionnaire which suited the main purpose of the study. A total of 289 fully completed questionnaires were retrieved. The data obtained were tallied, summarized, coded and presented in frequency Tables and percentages. Among the results were ongoing administration of BCG (60.2%), DPT (64.7%), polio (80.6%) and measles vaccines (88.2%) at Zaakpon PHC centre. There was a good utilization of health services as seen in the increasing number of children immunized each year until the communal crisis erupted. Furthermore, this study revealed a reduction in the morbidity and mortality for the six childhood killer diseases. Reduction in morbidity was approximately 3 times between the period of 2014 and 2017. It was, therefore, recommended that more frequent health seminar be given on immunization and house to house campaign from time to time within the study area for radical health education and health promotion.

Keywords: Impact, immunization, under-5 children, and Zaakpon.